

ISic1562

I.Sicily inscription 1562

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

tuff

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova,Valentina Mignosa

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Selinus

Place of origin (modern)

Selinunte

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Palermo, Museo Archeologico

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [---]KIAION

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 285088

EDR 120810

EDCS 41300043

PHI 175654

Bibliography

Manni Piraino, M.T. 1973. *Iscrizioni greche lapidarie del Museo di Palermo. Sikelika 6*. Palermo. At 59

Arena, R. 1996. *Iscrizioni Greche Archaiche di Sicilia e Magna Grecia*. *Iscrizioni*

di Sicilia. I. Iscrizioni di Megara Iblea e Selinunte. Pisa. At no.42
Gabrici, E. 1927. Il Santuario della Malophoros a Selinunte. *Monumenti Antichi*.
32: 5-419. At 384 no.11
Calder, W. M. 1964. Further notes on IG XIV 268 and other tufa inscriptions
from Selinus. *Greek, Roman and Byzantine Studies*. 5: 113-122. At 120
Manni Piraino, M.T. 1970. Epigrafia selinuntina. *Kokalos*. 16: 268-294. At 278
no.3
Grotta, C. 2010. Zeus Meilichios a Selinunte. Rome. At 111-112 no.4 tav.26b

Licensed under a Creative
Commons-Attribution 4.0 licence.

Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1562. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI
edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4354458>